

Assessment of Sensitivity Pattern of Tuberculosis in Response to 1st Line Anti Tuberculosis Drugs.

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Abstract:

Objective: The main aim of this study was to find the sensitivity pattern of tuberculosis to 1st line of antibiotics.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was carried out in Pulmonology department of Mayo hospital Lahore in a duration of 10 months from March 2018 to December 2019.

Type of Study: Cross sectional.

Materials and Methods: Patients were selected without gender discrimination having age greater than 15 years. Exclusion criteria included the patients who had already used ATT. LJ medium was used for sputum analysis for six weeks. Sensitivity of Mycobacterium was analyzed to 1st line of antibiotics. 2 mcg of streptomycin, 100 mcg for pyrazinamide, 0.2 mcg for isoniazid, 5 mcg of ethambutol and 1 mcg of rifampicin were the standard dose of drugs which was used in LJ medium to check the sensitivity.

Results: A total of 115 cases were included in this study. Among these patients 72 (62.60%) were males. The mean age of patients was 35 years. In 36 (32.17%) of the cases drug resistance was seen and in some cases resistance was seen to more than 1 drug. Streptomycin was the most common drug to which Mycobacterium showed resistance and it included 19 (16.52%) of cases. Second most common involving 17 (14.78%) of cases was isoniazid. In 30 (26.08%) cases resistance was seen to only one drug. Only 2 cases showed resistance to three and four antibiotics.

Conclusion: Almost every third case is resistant to TB antibiotics and highest resistance is seen in case of streptomycin.

Keywords: ATT. Lowenstein Jensen medium, MTB

Introduction: Tuberculosis is one of the oldest diseases known to mankind. Incidence rate is very high in underdeveloped countries like Pakistan and India. Although the incidence rate was decreasing initially in developed countries but with the rise of

HIV incidence rate is again at a rising pattern in developed countries as well. ¹⁻³

Bases of the site it is classified into pulmonary or extra pulmonary. Gold standard investigations for the diagnosis include sputum culture, blood culture along with radiological imaging for pulmonary TB. Location of extra pulmonary TB is usually helpful in diagnosis of EPTB. Multiple tests are available for the diagnosis but gene xpert is gold standard and costs less in comparison with cultures. ¹⁻⁸ Four antibiotics including rifampicin, ethambutol, isoniazid and pyrazinamide constitutes the initial standard therapy. In 1st line of antibiotics injectable one is streptomycin. Different categories are available based on different resistance to drugs by MTB.

The duration of treatment is very long and these high potency antibiotics are associated with wide range of side effects. This long duration is the main reason in resistance development and decreased efficacy. ¹³⁻¹⁶

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common involving 17 (14.78%) of cases was isoniazid. In 30 (26.08%) cases resistance was seen to only one drug. Only 2 cases showed resistance to three and four antibiotics.

Table 1: Study variables (n= 115)

Variable	Number	Percentage
Male	72	62.60%
Female	43	37.40%
Variable	Mean ± SD	Range
Age (years)	35.19±10.67	15-71
BMI (Kg/m ²)	24.33±4.19	15-31
Duration of symptoms (months)	3.78±0.67	1-6

Table 2: Resistance to drugs (n= 115)

Drugs	Number	Percentage
Streptomycin	19	16.52%
Isoniazid	17	14.78%
Pyrazinamide	5	4.35%
Rifampicin	3	2.60%
Ethambutol	3	2.60%

Table 3: Number of drugs with resistance (n= 115)

Drugs	Number	Percentage
1 drug	30	26.08%
2 drug	07	6.08%
3 drug	02	1.73%
4 drug	02	1.73%
None	68	59.13%

Discussion: Tuberculosis is one of the deadliest diseases known to mankind but with the development of modern medication a cure is possible but that includes proper dosage for a long duration and strict compliance. The emerging drug resistance caused by multiple factors like poor

compliance of the patient, unavailability of medicine, long duration and high number of side effects is the main issue.¹⁷⁻²⁰

In current study, 36 (32.17%) of the cases of drug resistance were seen and in some cases resistance was seen to more than 1 drug. These findings are in

accordance with past studies. Similar results were seen in a study conducted by Haq M et al in which he also found that maximum number of cases showed resistance to streptomycin which was seen in 19.05% of cases. Second most common resistance was seen in case if isoniazid reaching up to 14.9% of cases followed by ethambutol 3.4% and pyrazinamide 2.3%. The minimum resistance was seen in case of rifampicin which included only 2.3% cases. ⁶ The cause of high resistance can be attributed to the factor that the 1st drug developed to treat TB was streptomycin and high exposure rate led to the development of resistance. ¹⁸ In our study, 30 (26.08%) cases showed resistance to only one drug. 2 (1.73%) cases showed

resistance to three and four cases. One or more drug resistance is seen in almost 4.8% of all cases of TB as shown by WHO. The largest number of resistant TB cases are seen in India and China reaching to 50%. Among the rankings of TB resistant cases, Pakistan is at 4th number. ²¹⁻²² This high incidence rate of resistant TB strains is attributed to the excessive misuse of streptomycin for simple infections in far flung areas which has led to increased resistance.

Conclusion: Almost every third case is resistant to TB antibiotics and highest resistance is seen in case of streptomycin.

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